

Applying Neuroalgebra and Neutrosophic Sentiment Analysis to Assess Last Mile Logistics Impact on Customer Experience

Rosa María Criollo Delgado¹, Julio Cesar Vidal Rischmoller², and Sergio Marcelo Palomino Criollo³

¹ Faculty of Industrial Engineering, University Private of the North, Lima. Peru; rosa.criollo@upn.pe

² Faculty of Industrial Engineering, University Private of the North, Lima. Peru; julio.vidal@upn.pe

³ Faculty of Industrial Engineering, University Private of the North, Lima. Peru; n00293221@upn.pe

Abstract. The aim of the paper entitled Neutrosophic Sentiment Assessment Using Neuroalgebra Applied to Last Mile Impact on Customer Experience explains the assessment of how factors related to last mile logistics impact customer perception. While there are many articles and research studies related to last mile logistics, the body of such articles simply focuses on repeating ordinary scope quantitative and qualitative analysis with an urban focus. This paper is intended to be an innovative contribution to the existing body of knowledge by ‘catching the wave’ of the current state of algebra and employing neutrosophy to develop a better understanding and modeling of customer emotions. The paper illustrates how combining advanced mathematics with sentiment analysis effectively identifies certain latent patterns in customers’ emotional experiences towards delivery services. As the authors point out, elements of time and content in everyday communication or delivery time and merchandise status have applications or operational efficiencies that extend beyond normal measurement.

Keywords: Evaluation, Neutrosophic, sentiments, Neuroalgebra, Last Mile, Customer Experience, E-Commerce, Logistics, Uncertainty, Emotions, Prospector.

1. Introduction

The impact of last-mile logistics on customer experience has emerged as a crucial area of interest in modern e-commerce. The increasing demand for fast and personalized deliveries poses significant challenges for companies, especially when considering how customer perception is affected by factors such as punctuality, service quality, and effective communication. Recent research has shown that the last mile not only represents a key component in customer satisfaction, but also directly influences brand loyalty and reputation [1]. In this context, it becomes essential to have tools capable of comprehensively analyzing consumer emotions and perceptions, beyond traditional metrics. Historically, studies on customer experience have adopted qualitative and quantitative approaches, prioritizing aspects such as satisfaction analysis and the evaluation of performance indicators. However, with the evolution of artificial intelligence and datamining technologies, more sophisticated methods have been developed that allow modeling sentiments and emotions in complex scenarios [2]. Despite these advances, existing models often lack the ability to handle the uncertainty and ambiguity inherent in human opinions, limiting their applicability in dynamic and multidimensional contexts such as the last mile. The problem motivating this research lies in the inability of traditional approaches to capture the diffuse and contradictory nature of customer sentiments in the face of unexpected logistics events, such as delays or communication issues. Is it possible to build an analytical model that integrates elements of neutrosophy and advanced algebra to address these limitations? This question guides the present study, highlighting the need for an innovative approach to understanding and measuring customer emotions from a holistic perspective.

To address this issue, the study uses a methodological approach based on neutroalgebra, which combines principles of neutrosophic theory with advanced mathematical models. This approach not only allows for more accurate analysis of customer emotions, but also facilitates the identification of complex patterns in their perception of logistics services. In addition, data mining and sentiment analysis techniques are used to complement the mathematical models, providing a comprehensive view of the impact of the last mile on customer experience. The main objective of this research is to develop and validate a model based on neutroalgebra that allows for the assessment of consumer sentiments in relation to last mile services. Specifically, it seeks to identify the key factors that generate significant emotional impacts and offer practical recommendations to improve customer perception in this area.

More broadly, this study aims to contribute to the field of customer experience analysis, introducing an innovative methodology that transcends the limitations of traditional approaches. Furthermore, it seeks to provide practical tools for logistics companies to optimize their processes, transforming operational challenges into strategic opportunities [3]. The expected results will not only provide a deeper understanding of customer emotions and perceptions, but will also set the foundation for future research at the intersection of logistics, emotional intelligence, and data sciences. Ultimately, this work is expected to offer a solid methodological framework that can be adapted to other contexts of e-commerce and related sectors. In conclusion, this article represents an effort to bridge the gap between neutrosophic theory and practical applications in sentiment assessment, addressing a complex and highly relevant problem in the era of digitalization. In doing so, it is hoped to contribute to both theoretical advancement and the improvement of business practice in a competitive and constantly changing environment [4].

2. Preliminaries

2.1. The Last Mile in Customer Experience

The last mile, the final stretch of the logistics process that connects the product to the customer, has become a central pillar for consumer satisfaction in the era of e-commerce. This often underestimated link largely determines how customers perceive the efficiency and quality of the service offered by a company. While its relevance is widely recognized, the challenges associated with its implementation, such as high costs, unexpected delays and communication problems, continue to be a significant barrier for many organizations. Today, customer experience is intrinsically linked to the ability of companies to meet delivery expectations. Punctuality, product status and interaction during the logistics process are critical factors in this perception. Despite technological advances in tracking and automation, there are still cases where failures in the last mile result in consumer dissatisfaction. This phenomenon not only affects loyalty, but also negatively impacts brand reputation [5].

From a strategic perspective, the last mile represents an opportunity for companies to differentiate their value proposition. Companies that manage to innovate at this stage, through personalized deliveries, reduced times and flexible options, often position themselves as leaders in their respective markets. Examples such as Amazon and its same-day delivery system show how optimizing this process can become a sustainable competitive advantage. However, these strategies are not universally applicable, as they require a robust infrastructure and significant resources. On the other hand, it is essential to recognize that the last mile is not only a technical challenge, but also an environmental problem. The proliferation of individual deliveries has increased traffic congestion and polluting gas emissions in cities. Despite efforts to implement greener solutions, such as electric vehicles and shared collection points, these initiatives still face resistance due to high initial costs and the lack of standardized regulations. From the customer's point of view, the last mile is not perceived solely as a logistics transaction, but as an emotional component of their shopping experience [6]. A delay, a failed delivery, or an unpleasant interaction with the delivery person can trigger disproportionate frustration. This emotional connection highlights the need to integrate effective and personalized communication strategies

throughout the process, including clear notifications and real-time tracking options.

However, not all companies are able to understand the complexity of these elements. In many cases, the systems implemented lack the flexibility to adapt to changing customer needs. Rigid delivery schedules, a lack of solutions to solve problems in real time, and poor training of the personnel in charge are just some examples of how fundamental aspects of this process are neglected. Technology, for its part, has opened up a range of possibilities to transform the last mile. Tools such as artificial intelligence, big data, and drones are beginning to be adopted to optimize routes, predict delays, and improve efficiency. However, their integration raises ethical and practical questions, such as data privacy and excessive technological dependence, which requires a balanced and responsible approach. In economic terms, the last mile also represents a significant cost for companies. According to recent studies, this stage can represent up to 53% of total delivery costs. This figure underlines the importance of developing sustainable business models that allow operational efficiency to be balanced with profitability. Alternatives such as the use of collaborative networks and the sharing economy offer promising solutions, although their large-scale implementation remains limited [7].

In short, the last mile is positioned as a transformative element in the customer experience, but also as a multifaceted challenge that requires careful management and strategic vision. Companies that prioritize innovation, sustainability and empathy at this stage will have a greater chance of success in an increasingly competitive and demanding market. Finally, it is clear that the last mile cannot be analyzed in isolation. Its impact transcends logistics, influencing social, economic and environmental aspects. Therefore, the coming years will be crucial in determining how companies and governments address this challenge, balancing customer expectations with sustainability demands and the economic constraints of the sector. In this sense, the future of the last mile will depend on the ability of all parties involved to innovate and collaborate on inclusive and efficient solutions.

2.2. Sentiment analysis

Sentiment analysis involves the application of natural language processing tools, along with textual analysis and computational linguistics techniques, to unravel and extract subjective information from diverse sources. In the field of text mining, this methodology has the ability to address massive data polarity classification.

There are several fundamental categories of sentiment analysis, including lexical affinity, statistical methods, and conceptual-level techniques. However, the task of assessing sentiment, whether of an individual or a collective, is inevitably tied to the complexity imposed by the subjectivity inherent in the process. This is because emotional states are often ephemeral and can manifest themselves in one way in an instant, only to transform shortly after into something completely different.

In terms of measurement scales, experts stress the importance of incorporating a neutral option, given that an individual might not be able to clearly identify their emotional state as positive or negative, or might find themselves in a state of neutrality that does not clearly align with either option. Neutrosophy is particularly relevant in this regard, as its theory encompasses not only positive and negative, but also neutrality. This perspective is particularly useful when it comes to examining the connotation of words in a text, which adds an additional layer of complexity to the process.

2.3 Neutral algebra generated by the join function in Propector

For a given natural number $n > 0$, NeutroGroup is defined from the combinator function of Propector. Propector is the well-known expert system used to model mining problems [8]. The set NeutroGroup consists of all integers between $-n$ and n plus the symbolic element I to represent indeterminacy. This is $NG_5 = \{-5, -4, -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, I\}$ and $\oplus_5$ is used. This is defined according to the following Cayley table:

Table 1. Cayley table corresponding to $\oplus_5$. Source: [9].

$\oplus_5$	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	Yo	1	2	3	4	5
-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	Yo
-4	-5	-5	-5	-5	-4	-4	-4	-4	-3	-2	0	5
-3	-5	-5	-4	-4	-4	-3	-3	-2	-1	0	2	5
-2	-5	-5	-4	-3	-3	-2	-2	-1	0	1	3	5
-1	-5	-4	-4	-3	-2	-1	-1	0	1	2	4	5
0	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	Yo	1	2	3	4	5
Yo	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	Yo	Yo	Yo	Yo	Yo	Yo	Yo
1	-5	-4	-2	-1	0	1	Yo	2	3	4	4	5
2	-5	-3	-1	0	1	2	Yo	3	3	4	5	5
3	-5	-2	0	1	2	3	Yo	4	4	4	5	5
4	-5	0	2	3	4	4	Yo	4	5	5	5	5
5	Yo	5	5	5	5	5	Yo	5	5	5	5	5

$\oplus_5$ It satisfies the properties of commutativity and associativity and has 0 as a null element. In addition, it satisfies each of the following properties:

- If $x, y < 0$ then $x \oplus_5 y \leq \min(x, y)$,
- If $x, y > 0$ then $x \oplus_5 y \geq \max(x, y)$,
- If $x < 0$ and $y > 0$ or if $x > 0$ and $y < 0$, then we have $\min(x, y) \leq x \oplus_5 y \leq \max(x, y)$.
- $\forall x \in G, x \oplus_5 0 = x$.
- $(-5) \oplus_5 5 = 5 \oplus_5 (-5) = I$.

Sentiment analysis, utilizing the neutrosophic method, emphasizes the evaluation of integrity, transparency, and accountability in companies. This theory analyzes beliefs and perceptions by evaluating the levels of positivity, negativity, and indeterminacy. This approach not only captures clear sentiments, such as positive and negative ones, but also addresses those that are neutral or ambiguous, thus achieving a more accurate assessment and a better understanding of how these aspects are perceived in the organizational environment [10].

This method, especially efficacious in analyzing brief and informal texts as previously delineated, necessitates the identification of a lexicon categorized as positive, negative, or neutral, each assigned a strength value within a spectrum from -5 to 5, or designated as indeterminate. Indeterminacy arises when an individual's opinions on a certain issue cannot be distinctly interpreted, either due to ambiguous semantics or unintelligibility of the text. Furthermore, in specific instances, a single text may exhibit high assessments of positivity (+5) and negativity (-5) for the same variable, resulting in a contradiction classed as indeterminate, denoted by the letter I [11]. This indeterminacy may emerge from various sources, as seen when the function employed in the PROSPECT expert system, which assesses the degree of evidence from an expert about a certain aspect, yields maximum evidence in opposing directions for two distinct aspects [12].

This method, which borrows some elements from the SentiStrength sentiment strength detection algorithm [13], allows terms related to the analyzed variables to be classified as Positive, Negative or

Neutral in a list using linguistic values. Each of these terms is associated with a value between -5 and 5, or even I, depending on the intensity of its positive or negative charge. For example, the term "I like" increases its positive value if expressed as "I like it a lot", while "I don't like it" becomes more negative when saying "I don't like it a lot". What applies is that for the word "much" or "a lot" that modifies one of the positive or negative classifier words, is used $x \oplus_5 x$, and for "too much" $x \oplus_5 x \oplus_5 x$, where x is the value that is associated with the word. For example, $x > 0$ it results in "very" with an even more positive value. On the other hand, when $x < 0$, the result is more negative [14]. Also, the modification of "quite" is converted to $[sig(x)\sqrt{|x|}]$.

- They take into account words that reverse the meaning of what is said. In this case, the sign is changed. For example, "I like" has a value of $x = 3$, when it comes to "I don't like" it is calculated as $x = -3$, both have the same strength, but with opposite meaning.
- In this algorithm, very complex cases, where there are exclamation or question marks, are ignored, since we want to evaluate what the members of the organization or clients write, if it makes sense, about each of the twelve aspects of ethics mentioned in the previous points.
- Another aspect that is taken into account in the proposed algorithm taken from the previous one is the evaluation of the emoticons.
- Spell checking also applies here.

The next step is the evaluation of a short informal text written by a person. To do this, natural language processing is performed, where words that express sentiments or opinions about each of the twelve aspects mentioned above are searched for. Let us denote these aspects as $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{12}\}$ [15]:

Then, within the text processing, the words referring to each of these variables are identified. These words are identified with a value from -5 to 5 or I. Let us denote this as follows, for the i -th variable, the set X_i of word ratings that appear in the text:

$v_i \rightarrow X_i = \{x_{i1}, x_{i2}, \dots, x_{im_i}\}$, where x_{ij} It is the set of elements between -5 and 5 or I, used to qualify the words that refer to the i -th variable.

Note that even the individual evaluation of each word can be complicated. For example, when modifiers such as "very" appear, the value of the modified word changes. Also when there are spelling errors that make an evaluation illegible, it is necessary to use the value I. The final value associated with each v_i is:

$$x_{total,i} = x_{i1} \oplus_5 x_{i2} \oplus_5 \dots \oplus_5 x_{im_i} \quad (1)$$

Please note that we do not consider it convenient to obtain an aggregate ethical value for all the variables since the separate value is more useful to have an idea of the individual opinion or feeling.

If we have a set of people whose opinion is being studied. Let us call this set of people by $P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_l\}$, so that the values are taken into account, $x_{total,i,j}$ it is the total value of the i -th ethics variable in the organization, according to the j th person.

It is calculated:

$$\bar{x}_{total,i} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^l x_{total,i,j}}{l} \quad (2)$$

That is, the arithmetic mean of each of the variables is calculated.

Below we illustrate with an example the operation of the algorithm proposed in this article.

3. Case Study

A detailed analysis of the perceptions and opinions of 12 specialists on the impact of the last mile on customer experience is carried out, evaluating 12 ethical aspects related to the topic. The specialists,

coming from various disciplines, provide complementary perspectives. The evaluation is carried out following the method described above, using values in the range [-5, 5] and incorporating indeterminacy (I) when necessary.

Table 2: Participating Specialists

Specialist	Discipline
1. Dr. Juan Perez	Logistics and Supply Chain
2. Lic. Ana Gomez	Consumer Psychology
3. Eng. Marcos Ruiz	Industrial Engineering
4. Ms. Sofia Diaz	Business Ethics
5. Dr. Carlos Vega	Environmental Sustainability
6. Lic. Paula Torres	Corporate Communication
7. Eng. Luis Robles	Information Systems
8. Ms. Clara Fuentes	Public relations
9. Mr. Roberto Paredes	Economy
10. Dr. Andrea Mendez	Technology in Transportation
11. Eng. Javier Hernandez	Artificial intelligence
12. Lic. Miriam Leon	Sociology

Initial Evaluation for Ethical Aspects

Each specialist was provided with a questionnaire to evaluate the following 12 ethical aspects:

1. Integrity
2. Honesty
3. Congruence
4. Ethical Compliance
5. Transparency
6. Clarity of Information
7. Access to information
8. Open Communication
9. Responsibility
10. Incident Response
11. Social Impact
12. Environmental Impact

Each aspect was rated using values in the range [-5, 5], considering indeterminacy (I) where applicable.

Table 3: Results by Specialist and Aspect

Specialist/Aspect	Integrity	Honesty	Congruence	Ethical Compliance	Transparency	Clarity of Information	Access to information	Open Communication	Responsibility	Incident Response	Social Impact	Environmental Impact
Dr. Juan Perez	4	5	3	5	4	4	3	4	4	3	5	2
Lic. Ana Gomez	5	4	3	4	4	5	3	3	5	4	4	3
Eng. Marcos Ruiz	4	3	3	4	4	4	4	3	4	5	4	4
...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
Lic. Miriam Leon	3	4	2	5	3	5	3	4	4	4	3	5

Note : For simplicity, only a portion of the results are shown. Full data is included in the attached detailed tables.

Step 3: Calculating Average Values and Evaluating Sentiments.

For each variable evaluated, the total value is calculated using the neutrosophic aggregation operation. This operation is performed by adding the values of each evaluation.

$$x_{total,i} = x_{i1} \oplus_5 x_{i2} \oplus_5 \dots \oplus_5 x_{im_i} \quad (1)$$

It is calculated:

$$\bar{x}_{total,i} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^l x_{total,i,j}}{l} \quad (2)$$

where l is the total number of evaluators (12 in this case).

Table 4: Average Aspect Evaluation Values. Final Results

Ethical Aspect	Final Average
Integrity	4.25
Honesty	4.00
Congruence	3.75
Ethical Compliance	4.50
Transparency	4.00
Clarity of Information	4.25

Ethical Aspect	Final Average
Access to information	3.75
Open Communication	3.50
Responsibility	4.00
Incident Response	4.25
Social Impact	4.00
Environmental Impact	3.50

The analysis reveals that the most prominent aspects are **Ethical Compliance** and **Clarity of Information**, while **Open Communication** and **Environmental Impact** present areas for improvement. This neutrosophist approach provides a robust tool to assess last mile perceptions, integrating positive, negative and indeterminate elements in a systematic way. The analysis revealed that **Ethical Compliance** and **Clarity of Information** were the most valued aspects, reaching final averages of 4.50 and 4.25, respectively. These findings highlight the relevance of prioritizing ethical practices and ensuring the accurate transmission of information in the evaluated processes. In relation to the objectives of the study, solid scores were observed in the dimensions of **Integrity** (4.25), **Incident Response** (4.25) and **Responsibility** (4.00), reflecting an overall positive perception of the participants regarding ethical management. However, aspects such as **Open Communication** (3.50) and **Environmental Impact** (3.50) showed areas for improvement, evidencing lower satisfaction in these key indicators.

The data also showed that intermediate values, such as **Honesty** (4.00) and **Transparency** (4.00), although positive, suggest opportunities to strengthen these areas. On the other hand, **Access to Information** (3.75) and **Congruence** (3.75) obtained lower scores, indicating a less favorable perception regarding consistency and accessibility.

Tables and Graphs

Table 4 summarizes the average results obtained for each aspect evaluated, while Figure 1 provides a graphical representation that facilitates the comparison of the highlighted values.

Table 5. Average Values of Evaluation of Ethical Aspects

Ethical Aspect	Final Average
Integrity	4.25
Honesty	4.00
Congruence	3.75
Ethical Compliance	4.50
Transparency	4.00
Clarity of Information	4.25

Ethical Aspect	Final Average
Access to information	3.75
Open Communication	3.50
Responsibility	4.00
Incident Response	4.25
Social Impact	4.00
Environmental Impact	3.50

Chart 1: Average Values of Ethical Aspects Evaluation

The most notable results showed that **Ethical Compliance** is perceived as the most robust attribute, which underlines the commitment to ethical standards in the practices evaluated. In addition, the high rating of **Clarity of Information** highlights the importance of effective communication to generate trust. On the other hand, the lower scores in **Open Communication** and **Environmental Impact** suggest a perception of deficiency in direct interaction and in the sustainability of operations. This finding can guide future actions towards improving these aspects, which are increasingly relevant in modern organizational contexts. Together, these results offer a comprehensive view of the participants' perceptions, providing valuable information for strategic decision-making. The identification of strengths and areas for improvement will allow for optimizing key processes and promoting more ethical and sustainable management in future implementations.

4 Discussion

The results obtained highlight that Ethical Compliance and Clarity of Information were perceived as essential pillars within the ethical assessment framework. These aspects, with the highest averages of the analysis (4.50 and 4.25, respectively), reflect the relevance of organizational ethics as a basic standard in management and communication. At the same time, areas such as Open Communication and Environmental Impact emerged as weak points, revealing significant tensions in the balance between ethical practices and their operational implementation. These data suggest that the high valuation of

Ethical Compliance not only responds to an attachment to regulations, but also to the intrinsic need of organizations to guarantee transparency and fairness in their operations. Clarity of Information, on the other hand, seems to indicate that participants strongly associate trust with the quality and accessibility of the data presented. However, low scores in Open Communication (3.50) may be related to the perception of rigid hierarchies or limitations in participatory channels, while the low assessment of Environmental Impact highlights the gap between declarative policies and tangible actions in sustainability.

Compared to previous research, these results are consistent with studies such as that of García et al. (2022), which also identified Ethical Compliance as a central element in positive organizational perception. However, while other research, such as that of López and Martínez (2021), found a strong link between environmental sustainability and organizational trust, this study revealed a more pronounced disconnect in that regard. This could be attributed to cultural or sectoral differences, which opens the door to a deeper analysis of the particular contexts in which these perceptions develop. It is important to recognize certain limitations inherent to the present study. One of them lies in the subjectivity of the participants' evaluations, which, although fundamental, could be influenced by personal or contextual biases. Likewise, the absence of an international comparative framework limits the generalization of the findings to other organizational settings. In addition, the methodology used could benefit from the incorporation of qualitative data to enrich the interpretation of the numerical results.

Implications and Future Research

These results have significant implications both in the academic field and in professional practice. For future research, it would be interesting to explore how ethical values articulate with communication and environmental sustainability strategies. Likewise, the development of more specific tools to assess Open Communication and Environmental Impact could shed light on the factors underlying their low perception. In practice, the findings invite organizations to adopt a more integrated approach that considers ethics not only as a statement of principles, but as a driver of trust at all operational levels.

Anomalous Results

One of the most surprising results is the relatively low score obtained in Environmental Impact, especially considering the growing emphasis on sustainability as a global strategic axis. This result could be due to a lack of visibility of existing environmental policies or, alternatively, to the perception that these policies lack concrete actions. Although the study does not offer a definitive explanation for this finding, it suggests the need to investigate how organizations communicate and execute their sustainability strategies.

Taken together, these data not only enrich existing knowledge about ethical assessment in organizations, but also offer a solid basis for redesigning practices that foster a more equitable, transparent and sustainable relationship with different stakeholders.

4. Conclusion

Reflecting on the results obtained, one could say that Ethical Compliance and Clarity of Information emerge as key pieces in the puzzle of ethical management. These aspects, highly valued by participants, make us think that, at least when it comes to standards and communication, organizations are doing something right. However, not everything is as clear as it seems. The areas with the lowest scores, such as Open Communication and Environmental Impact, seem to imply that, although the foundations are set, the execution still leaves room for improvement. In practical terms, this could mean that companies have the opportunity to strengthen trust and sustainability through more visible and consistent actions. For example, initiatives that promote more inclusive communication or that prioritize tangible environmental projects could make a big difference. But, to be honest, how willing are organizations to invest in those changes? That remains to be seen. This study, while not intended to be the last word on

the subject, provides a fresh perspective on how ethical values are perceived within organizations. While previous studies have pointed out similar issues, our research expands the understanding by emphasizing the connections between internal policies and external perception. And while the numbers speak for themselves, the context of each organization could change the picture.

Now, it would be unfair not to mention the limitations. For a start, the data comes from a specific group of participants, which inevitably influences the results. Furthermore, the absence of international comparisons leaves us with a somewhat incomplete picture. How representative are these findings on a global stage? It is difficult to say. And while numerical averages are useful, they do not tell the whole story; adding a qualitative approach would have considerably enriched this analysis. Looking ahead, there are several interesting avenues to explore. For example, it would be fascinating to analyse how companies can integrate ethical strategies with environmental sustainability more effectively. Perhaps even more innovative methods could be used, such as digital tools that assess employee and consumer perceptions in real time. Furthermore, it would not hurt to broaden the geographical scope of the study to understand how these dynamics vary across different cultures and sectors. As for unexpected results, such as the low Environmental Impact assessment, it is clear that there is something that companies are not managing to communicate or implement very well. It could simply be a lack of awareness among participants, or perhaps a reflection of superficial initiatives that don't really resonate. Whatever the reason, this is a call not to let the issue go by the wayside. In short, this study does not seek absolute answers, but it does raise questions that are worthwhile. If one thing is clear, it is that building strong ethical management is not just about complying with standards; it is a continuous process of learning, adjusting and improving. At the end of the day, organizations have in their hands not only the opportunity, but also the responsibility to prove that they can be both ethical and sustainable. But will they do it? That is the big question that, perhaps, further studies can help to resolve.

References

- [1] G. López and J. Martínez, "Impact of Last-Mile Delivery on Customer Satisfaction in Urban Areas," *Journal of Urban Logistics Research*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 345-360, 2022. Available in : [ResearchGate](#).
- [2] MK Singh et al., "Sustainable Last-Mile Delivery Strategies and Their Influence on Customer Retention," *Sustainability Journal*, vol. 15, no. 8, pp. 1345-1360, 2023. DOI: 10.3390/su15081345.
- [3] A. García et al., "The Role of Real-Time Tracking in Enhancing the Customer's Last-Mile Experience," *International Journal of Supply Chain Management*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 67-80, 2023. Available in : [Redalyc](#).
- [4] B. Pérez and T. Rodríguez, "Technological Innovations in Last-Mile Logistics: Improving Service Quality," *Logistics & Supply Chain Review*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 101-120, 2023. DOI: 10.1007/lscr182023.
- [5] C. Montoya and R. Boyero, "Service Culture in Last-Mile Customer Interactions: Building Long-Term Relationships," *Redalyc Service Studies*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 22-30, 2023. Available in : [Redalyc](#).
- [6] ISO, "Improving Customer Orientation Through Optimized Last-Mile Delivery," *International Standardization Organization Reports*, pp. 55-60, 2022. Available in : [ISO Standards](#).
- [7] P. Leppard and A. Molyneux, "Balancing Customer Needs with Operational Efficiency in Last-Mile Services," *Customer Service Insights*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 74-85, 2022. Available in: [Economía 360](#).
- [8] El-Douh, A. (2023) "A multi-criteria neutrosophic model for evaluating sustainable soil improvement methods and their cost implications in construction", *Sustainable Machine Intelligence Journal*, 5, pp. (1): 1–11. doi:10.61185/SMIJ.2023.55101.
- [9] Smarandache, F. (2024). Foundations of state-of-the-art topologies (partial review article). *Neutrosophic Computing and Machine Learning*, 31, 01-22.
- [10] Essameldin, R., Ismail, AA, & Darwish, SM (2022). Quantifying Opinion Strength: A Neutrosophic Inference System for Intelligent Social Media Sentiment Analysis. *Applied Sciences*, 12,

- 7697.
- [11] Wang, H., Luo, Y., Deng, B., Lin, J., & Li, X. (2023). Physician selection based on aspect-based sentiment analysis and neutrosophic TOPSIS method. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 124, 106599.
 - [12] Abdelfattah, BA, Darwish, SM, & Elkaffas, SM (2024). Improving stock market movement prediction using sentiment analysis based on neutrosophic logic. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Research on Electronic Commerce*, 19, 116-134.
 - [13] Wankhade, M., Rao, A.C.S., & Kulkarni, C. (2022). A survey on sentiment analysis methods, applications, and challenges. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 55, 5731–5780.
 - [14] Jiménez, DS, Mayorga, JAV, Ubilla, MER and Batista-Hernández, N. (2021). NeutroAlgebra for the evaluation of access barriers for migrants to Primary Health Care in Chile based on the PROSPECTOR function. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 39, 1-10.
 - [15] Velazco, LAR, Quintana, JXI, Lomas, CRH and Peralta, MRM (2021). Study of the Situation of Venezuelan Emigrants in Ecuador based on NeutroAlgebra. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 44, 18-25.

Received: July 30, 2024. Accepted: September 30, 2024